

MODELLING STRATEGIES FOR TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of modelling strategies for processing and performance characteristics of textile composites. The methodology employed by the authors is to utilise a simple yet general formalism that applies to an unlimited range of textile structures. At this stage most applications have centred on woven (2D and 3D), braided, knitted and non-crimp (multiaxial warp-knit) fabrics. Starting with a simple definition of the interlacing pattern, the geometry of the textile reinforcement is built. From this definition the volume surrounding the tows is generated and split into simple basic volumes following precise criteria, allowing the unit cell (or larger representative volume) to be discretised in a predictable and robust way. Most importantly, all of these steps are accomplished within automated software tools that require simple inputs understandable to the textile manufacturer.

Once the textile structure and unit cell geometry have been identified, these can be used within any desired calculation method. For example, the discretised geometry can be imported into CFD software to investigate flow properties and to determine the permeability tensor for simulations of liquid composite moulding. The same geometry can be imported into a structural FE code to predict elastic properties and stress distributions. These approaches are likely to give accurate results at a penalty in terms of CPU time. The authors are developing fast, simple approaches to produce predictions more rapidly. This paper outlines the modelling approach used for textile composite unit cells, and provides examples of predictions for permeability and mechanical properties. These are illustrated for a range of textile structures.

KEYWORDS: unit cell, representative volume element, permeability, mechanical properties, Monte-Carlo method

INTRODUCTION

Textile composites, consisting of textile reinforcements within a thermoplastic or thermoset polymer matrix, can offer an efficient and cost effective solution for a range of applications. However given the large number of materials and processes available to the designer, there is a need for an integrated predictive modelling approach. The problem is further complicated by deformations and distortions to the fibre architecture that occur during three-dimensional forming, and by statistical variations resulting from ply placement and variability in the textile structure. To allow materials to be selected efficiently, predictive models are required for processing properties (such as permeability or formability) and subsequent mechanical performance based on constituent (reinforcement/matrix) properties and the fibre architecture.

The authors are developing a number of predictive modelling strategies for processing and performance of textile composites. At the mesoscopic scale, these are based on a simple geometric model for the fibre architecture. This model can be used within any desired calculation method, and interfaces are being developed to automatically generate input files for various process and performance models. In this paper, the geometric modelling strategy is described and a number of down-stream calculation methods are discussed. In particular various predictive modelling strategies are proposed for both textile permeability and composite mechanical properties. Finally statistical variations to these properties are explored, and strategies for analysing these are discussed.

GEOMETRIC MODELLING OF THE UNIT CELL

A number of models have been proposed in the past for textile reinforcements [eg. 1, 2]. Lomov *et al* have developed a hierarchical model for textiles, where tow (or yarn) geometries are determined using an energy based approach [3]. This offers perhaps the most accurate geometric description available, and has been applied to a wide range of textiles including woven and non-crimp fabrics. However the description relies on mechanical property data for the tows, which are not readily available. In addition published models appear to generate information related only to the textile itself, and not the volumes that surround the tows which are required to determine properties such as permeability and composite stress-strain response.

The present authors have developed a geometric modelling strategy based on a simple description for textile reinforcements. This is aimed at generating descriptions for practically any textile, using a simple yet universal definition of the fibre architecture. Starting from a vectorial description of the tow interlacing pattern, a series of geometric algorithms are utilised to generate tow/fibre paths and their surfaces. From this solid models of the tows/fibres and the volumes that surround them are generated. These volumes may be utilised within any subsequent analysis technique. Each step in the modelling procedure is automated using in-house software tools.

Figure 1. Textile geometric modelling steps: a) vectors; b) paths; c) sections; d) envelopes; e) lateral edges; f) some basic volumes

The geometric modelling procedure is demonstrated here for a monofilament HDPE flow enhancement fabric used in vacuum infusion (or VARTM), consisting of parallel chain stitches holding weft insertions. The modelling strategy consists of a number of stages, as illustrated in Figure 1 and described below:

1. Vectors are defined to describe the interlacing pattern (Fig. 1a), based on criteria for the non-equivocal definition of vectors described in previous publications [4, 5].
2. Tow or fibre paths are superimposed onto the vectors (Fig. 1b), using simple geometric curves (Bezier curves, circular arcs, or piecewise linear user defined paths).
3. Envelopes are created around the paths, by defining standard sections (elliptical, lenticular or user defined) along the paths (Fig. 1c). These are combined to create the envelope (Fig. 1d), and varying sections are automatically morphed to define a smoothed surface (for example to represent a non-crimp fabric where the tow section is modified in the vicinity of the stitching thread). Interference between tow or fibre surfaces is checked at this stage, allowing the description to be modified if required.
4. Basic volumes within the fibres/tows and empty volumes surrounding these are generated, by firstly projecting lateral edges onto the x-y plane (Fig. 1e), and then using these to identify the volume boundaries (Fig. 1f). These basic volumes are defined by upper and lower surfaces and a number of contiguous lateral surfaces.

The procedure allows the automated generation of predictable unit cell models. In practice, any textile will contain statistical variations in (for example) fibre/tow path and tow shape. To represent this, randomness can be introduced at all stages. Positions of the vector origins and ends, representing points where two different tows superimpose in the unit cell, can be randomised in the plane (where they move in unison) and/or along the thickness of the textile. Randomness can be introduced in tow sections. Randomness of paths and sections can be tuned locally to represent regions where the geometry is more variable, for example along large loops. Figure 2 shows 4 unit cells for a plain weave with different levels of randomness applied to the paths: the in-plane co-ordinates of each point where two tows superimpose follow normal distributions around their nominal values (Fig. 2a). Note that the 4 unit cells are not identical when randomness is introduced (Figs. 2b, c, d).

Figure 2. Randomness introduced on x,y positions of vectors ends for 4 unit cells of plain weave. Ratio of vector length to standard deviation of position: a) 0%, b) 5%, c) 10%, d) 13%

The software has many built-in geometric functions providing the user with accuracy, flexibility and ease of use. It also has a number of processing and output functions. Examples of this are file output to TecPlot™ and Gambit™, linking to powerful commercial solid modellers, mesh generators and format translators. Another example is file output to STL format, enabling usage of any STL viewer for geometry assessment. Figure 3 shows an example of information obtained from such a tool, here DeskArtes™ View Expert™. An interference detection scheme is operational in the author's software, and is being refined. Script command is under development. At present the software can be used to build geometric models very rapidly, for any textile. Export functions to commercial mesh generators allow any subsequent calculation to be conducted. A dedicated, faster post-processor developed by the authors is nearing completion and will make these calculations significantly faster. Script command will allow stochastic investigation to be conducted in an automated, productive way.

Figure 3. Section through 4 unit cells of plain weave with varying level of randomness on tow ends: a) 0%, b) 13%. Images produced with DeskArtes™ ViewExpert™.

PERMEABILITY PREDICTION

Predictions for reinforcement permeability may be developed from a three-dimensional unit cell geometry such as that described above, including the tows and the volumes between them. Provided that the model can be generated and imported into a flow modelling package easily, this offers an attractive option compared to experimental determination of the permeability tensor. For example Lomov *et al* [3] have implemented such a procedure based on a lattice-Boltzmann approach. The most rigorous approach is to utilise computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software, where directional permeability values may be determined by (for example) calculating the average velocity through a saturated domain subjected to a known pressure gradient. The tows may be modelled as orthotropic porous media using Darcy's law, whereas the volumes that surround them within the mould are modelled using Navier-Stokes. An example of this approach is shown in Figure 4 for flow around a single tow. In this case Fluent™ generates pressure values and components of the 3D velocity field at each point, enabling a direct calculation of the permeability of the full domain.

Figure 4. CFD analysis, eg. flow around an elliptical tow; a) 3D mesh, b) pressure distribution for flow across tow (red is high pressure, blue is lower pressure). The porous tow is not included here.

To obtain realistic results attention must be paid to the boundary conditions imposed. For example “no slip” conditions should only really be applied at solid boundaries, whereas interfaces between unit cells within a larger preform should be modelled as moving boundaries. Imposing a constant pressure gradient between the inlet and outlet faces may also not be appropriate, if for example the flow is divided between low and high permeability regions. For these reasons it may be necessary to model a number of unit cells to obtain a representative permeability value.

The above methodology requires significant effort, both in generation of the model and in subsequent CPU time. This makes the approach impractical for obtaining the range of permeability data required for an accurate RTM process model. For example, forming or draping of fabrics to three-dimensional components necessitates the generation of permeability data at a range of in-plane fabric shear angles and fibre volume fractions [6]. Consideration of statistical variations likely in fibre arrangements would increase the number of analyses required by at least an order of magnitude. Even if meshing of the domain were automated, the number of degrees of freedom (approximately 25 000 in Fig. 4) mean that it is not possible to conduct the large number of calculations required in a reasonable timescale.

To address these issues the authors are implementing an alternative procedure, termed the “stream-surface method”. In this approach, the model is reduced to what may be termed a 2.5D problem, as described in our earlier paper [7]. Essentially, bisector planes are defined within the basic volumes that describe the fibre tows and open channels. Each plane is discretised and either a thickness (open channels) or permeability tensor (porous tows) is associated with each node. The pressure distribution may be determined from the standard expression for saturated flow in porous media:

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\mu} [K] \nabla P \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $[K]$ is the permeability tensor, P is the pressure and μ is the resin viscosity. Permeabilities within the porous tows may be determined from a number of predictive models for flow within parallel fibre arrays, eg. Gebart [8]:

$$k_1 = \frac{8r^2}{c_1} \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (2)$$

$$k_2 = c_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_\infty}{V_f} - 1} \right)^{5/2} r^2 \quad (3)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the permeabilities parallel and perpendicular to the tow, V_f and V_∞ are the current and maximum possible fibre volume fractions, and c_1 and c_2 are parameters determined from the fibre arrangement. The tow direction is known at every position from the path generated by the geometric modelling procedure. Therefore the tow direction can be transformed to determine the global in-plane permeability tensor components, if not parallel to the global axes (as will usually be the case). For empty volumes surrounding the tows, the channel thickness, h , is used to determine an equivalent channel permeability, $h^2/12$.

Once the pressure distribution is known, the average flow velocity (or volume flow rate per unit section) can be determined using Darcy’s law and hence the permeability of the cell can be calculated. Velocities are usually resolved in zones where the local permeability is easily obtained. Accuracy of velocity can be verified by applying this procedure to a number of “slices” of the domain. Two solution approaches can be employed based on the stream-surface method. In Figure 5 the discretised domain is imported into an RTM flow simulation and a transient filling analysis is conducted. This allows the unsaturated permeability to be determined, and may also allow phenomena such as void entrapment to be modelled. Alternatively the pressure field can be determined using standard, non-iterative finite differences for a fully saturated domain. The former approach is clearly attractive to

potential end-users, since both permeability calculations and subsequent macroscopic RTM flow analyses can be conducted using the same software package. However the latter approach offers the fastest solution, and may therefore be preferred when a large number of cases are to be simulated for the same unit cell (eg. to represent fabric shear, compaction, and statistical variations).

Figure 5. Stream-surface modelling demonstration; a) 3D mesh, b) pressure distribution for flow across tow (red is high pressure, blue is lower pressure). The porous tow is not included here.

In an accompanying paper presented at this conference the authors show that values of directional permeability obtained from the stream-surface method are generally in excellent agreement with those predicted using CFD. The main advantage of the stream-surface approach is the reduction in degrees of freedom (typically by at least an order of magnitude) when compared to a full 3D model. This means that results can be obtained extremely quickly (for the saturated case, solutions can be obtained literally within seconds using a standard PC). The same model can be subjected to flow conditions in any direction, so that all principal permeability components (and their orientations) can be determined rapidly. However, there are a number of issues with the method. One is the issue of flow branching observed when flow is split by tows. Another is that resin cannot flow vertically from tow volumes to free volumes. At this stage these issues do not seem to affect the performance of the method for fairly thin preforms where relatively little flow occurs through the thickness. A systematic evaluation of the method is ongoing and the findings to date are presented in our accompanying paper.

More fundamentally, another important issue concerns the relevance of simulation methods (CFD, stream-surface or Lattice-Boltzman) for describing what happens in actual preforms. Whilst detailed flow field information can be obtained from CFD and Lattice-Boltzman one has to consider the accuracy of the geometric models used within these methods, especially in light of their requirements in CPU and time. It seems to the authors that the actual objective is to have a calculation method that provides a reasonable estimate of the permeability and is very fast. Such a method may be used in stochastic analysis to provide average values of directional permeabilities for any deformed textile, as well as estimates of the distribution of these values. It may then be possible to quantify the variability associated with composites processing and performance, and to design more robust manufacturing operations, configurations and equipment. The way to proceed may be to minimise the number of experiments to a small number for scaling purposes when fill time predictions are essential.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

As with prediction of permeability, an accurate 3D model for the textile unit cell facilitates prediction of mechanical properties. Several studies have been published recently on prediction of elastic properties and (to a much lesser extent) failure and post-failure. Various approaches exist: “mosaic” methods using laminate analysis to model the fibre direction at each point within the cell [9], methods using “voxels” (volume cells or 3D pixels) to represent local values of transformed UD properties which are then averaged using iso-stress or iso-strain assumptions [10], and 3D finite element modelling of the interwoven tows within an isotropic matrix [e.g. 11, 12]. The third approach is the

most rigorous but also the most labour-intensive and computationally expensive, although increasingly powerful computation makes this a promising route to pursue preferably via automated mesh generation. However, whilst some analyses are linked to fibre architecture models, none of the published models are for general fabrics rather than specific weaves, so that the 3D model must be constructed individually for each fibre architecture.

The geometric model described in this paper can be used to automate many of the steps in generation of a 3D unit cell model for structural FE analysis. A collection of basic volumes defining the fibre reinforced tow and matrix regions can be discretised using either commercial mesh generation packages or dedicated procedures. Within these the matrix may be modelled as isotropic and the impregnated tows as orthotropic (effectively transversely isotropic). Principal values for elastic constants can be predicted using standard micromechanical models, such as the rule of mixtures for longitudinal modulus and Poisson's ratio and Halpin-Tsai equations for transverse and shear moduli. Initial failure may be anticipated using, for example, von Mises criterion (for the matrix) and a simple non-interactive failure criterion for the impregnated tows (eg. maximum stress or Tsai-Hill).

Local fibre orientations can be determined from the tow path within the geometric model so that principal directions may be defined automatically on a per-element basis. Similarly local elastic constants and failure stresses, which may vary due to changes in fibre volume fraction from local tow cross-sections, can be generated automatically.

Examples are shown in Figure 6 and 7. Figure 6 shows the tows and matrix volumes for a $\pm 60^\circ$ laminate, as well as von Mises stresses when the laminate is subjected to tension along its main direction. Here the tows are perfectly straight, equally spaced and their section is the same everywhere. This type of solid model can be created very easily and does not justify using a dedicated textile modeller. Figure 7, on the other hand, shows von Mises stresses for the textile illustrated in Figure 1 subjected to a compressive load. Such a case would be difficult to model without a dedicated textile modeller and suitable file output procedures; stochastic analyses would be impossible to conduct within a reasonable time frame, even for a single unit cell such as shown.

Figure 6. Calculated stresses in a unit cell for a $\pm 60^\circ$ laminate; a) tow volumes, b) empty volume between tows, c) von Mises stresses under axial tension. tow (green is high stress, darker blue is lower stress).

Figure 7. Stresses in a unit cell for a warp-knitted textile; a) tows, b) matrix (red is high stress, blue is lower stress).

The main problem associated with FE analysis for a 3D solid unit cell model is the number of elements required for an accurate model. For the above models approximately 67 000 and 112 000 elements were required respectively. A unit cell for a plain weave requires typically more than 30 000 elements. This has implications both in terms of memory requirements and CPU times. However, as with permeability prediction there is potential to reduce the complexity of the problem. For example, thin laminates could be modelled in 2.5D using layered shell elements, where layer properties were generated as slices through the basic volumes. Potential future applications for this approach include damage during fatigue, impact loading, and post-failure properties.

MATERIAL VARIABILITY

One notable deficiency of existing analysis approaches for both component manufacture and subsequent mechanical performance is that they result in a single answer. Industrial experience rarely reflects this where, for a given component geometry, statistical variations in material properties can lead to a range of outcomes for a single combination of materials. This is evident in the RTM filling phase, where flow patterns and resulting cycle times are rarely the same for two supposedly identical mouldings. These variations may be traced to a number of sources, including variations in temperature (and hence resin viscosity) or injection conditions. However the reinforcement fibre architecture must contribute significantly to scatter during processing. Ply placement, nesting, and statistical variations to the fabric structure caused by handling will all lead to scatter in reinforcement permeability and hence flow behaviour. Advani *et al* [13] have investigated this problem thoroughly with regard to race-tracking due to poor ply placement. Recent studies by Pan *et al* [14] and Hoes *et al* [15] have demonstrated that repeated measurements of permeability for nominally identical stacks of textiles can be described reasonably by a normal distribution, with a standard deviation typically in the range 10-20% of the mean value. These distributions are almost certainly due to a combination of variable nesting and local distortions to the fibre pattern.

Mechanical properties for textile composites exhibit variations for similar reasons to those described above. Coupon tests for nominally identical specimens result in scatter in (for example) tensile modulus and ultimate tensile strength. The position of ultimate failure would appear to be different for each specimen tested. Hence one must expect some variation in mechanical performance between textile composite components. This problem may be addressed using stochastic analysis, where a series of analyses are performed to determine the results expected from a distribution of basic material

properties. Monte-Carlo methods can be adopted, where properties are chosen “randomly” from a known distribution to populate the modelling domain.

The authors are adopting stochastic analysis techniques on two levels. At the meso-scale (unit cell level) randomness can be included within the tow paths and sections automatically, following normal distributions for example as illustrated in Figure 2. A series of such unit cell models can be generated automatically and these can be analysed to determine distributions in textile permeability, composite mechanical properties and other processing and performance properties. A large number of analyses are required to obtain convergence in the predicted material properties, and hence efficient strategies such as the stream-surface method for permeability prediction are required. The authors are currently conducting systematic predictions of the effect of different geometric parameters on permeability and static mechanical properties. Initial findings are presented in accompanying papers. Such results provide clear insight into the effect of the intimate geometry of the preform, and they can be used in conjunction with a Monte-Carlo scheme in order to establish a distribution for different processing and performance properties.

At the macro-scale (component level), predicted or measured distributions in properties can be incorporated within RTM filling simulations and component structural FE analyses. Input files for these simulations are generated automatically by in-house software, with properties for each element generated using a Monte-Carlo method. For textile permeability following a normal distribution, the technique requires the generation of random numbers within the range $[0,1]$, which are used to determine appropriate property values from the cumulative probability distribution function. Figure 8 illustrates predicted locations for the last point to be filled in a rectangular mould injected from all four corners, obtained using the LIMS software from the University of Delaware. If permeability were identical for each element, one would expect the last point to fill to be in the centre of the mould. For Fig. 8a, the measured permeability distribution for a 2x2 twill weave glass fabric at 53% fibre volume fraction was used (mean value of $2.6 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and standard deviation of $5.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$, from [15]). Clearly there is significant scatter in predicted last points to fill, with results restricted to a relatively narrow band around the horizontal centre-line. Fig. 8b was obtained using the same procedure but with the standard deviation doubled. Now the scatter is increased significantly, with last point to fill located relatively close to one of the mould corners on a number of occasions.

Figure 8. Predicted last points to fill for rectangular plate injected simultaneously from all four corners. Results generated using a Monte-Carlo method: (a) measured permeability data for twill weave glass fabric; (b) same permeability data but with standard deviation doubled.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has described the development of a geometric model for textile composites, which can be used as the basis for property prediction at the meso-scale. Tow envelopes can be generated for any

textile and output to commercial solid modellers and mesh generators using automated interfaces. A number of features are being refined, such as an algorithm to detect interference between tows. However the software is now operational and can be used to generate models for prediction of processing properties (permeability) and mechanical performance. A number of modelling strategies, and associated issues, have been described here.

Given the wide variety of materials, processes and fibre architectures available, the authors believe that the only sensible approach to both process and structural design is via predictive modelling. The aim should be to minimise the number of experimental tests required, with models used to predict trends in material properties subjected to systematic changes in fibre architecture and tests used for scaling purposes (if at all). Consideration of variability in fibre architectures for real components, due to three-dimensional forming and to material variability, increases the scale of the problem further. The authors are considering variations in fibre architecture, including stochastic variations to tow paths and sections, at every stage of their analyses. Script command is being implemented, which will allow automated stochastic studies to be conducted. Novel and efficient calculation methods are being developed to allow property distributions to be predicted within a reasonable timescale. The stream-surface method for permeability has been developed by the authors over a number of years, and this has matured sufficiently to be systematically evaluated. Similar efficient methods for other properties are under development.

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